

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES NECESSARY FOR FUTURE SOCIAL WORK ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: This article presents professional competencies necessary for the effective implementation of social work activities. It emphasizes the need for a social worker to acquire a wide range of knowledge, including knowledge of natural, socio-humanitarian, economic, political and philosophical sciences.

Keywords: Social work, professional competencies, social groups, professional qualifications, social protection, social policy, legal guarantees, youth, families, health, employment policy.

BO'LAJAK IJTIMOYIY ISH FAOLIYATIDA ZARUR BO'LGAN PROFESSIONAL KOMPETENSIYALAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ijtimoiy ish faoliyatining samarali amalga oshirilishi uchun zarur bo'lgan professional kompetensiyalarni taqdim etadi. Ijtimoiy ish xodimi uchun keng qamrovli bilimlar, shu jumladan tabiiy, ijtimoiy-gumanitar, iqtisodiy, siyosiy va falsafiy fanlardan bilim olish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ijtimoiy ish, professional kompetensiyalar, ijtimoiy guruhlar, kasbiy malakalar, ijtimoiy himoya, ijtimoiy siyosat, huquqiy kafolatlar, yoshlar, oilalar, salomatlik, bandlik siyosati.

ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫЕ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ, НЕОБХОДИМЫЕ ДЛЯ БУДУЩЕЙ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ

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Аннотация: В статье представлены профессиональные компетенции, необходимые для эффективного осуществления деятельности социальной работы. Подчеркивается, что социальному работнику необходимо обладать широкой базой знаний, включающей знания в области естественных, социальных, гуманитарных, экономических, политических и философских наук.

Ключевые слова: Социальная работа, профессиональные компетенции, социальные группы, профессиональная квалификация, социальная защита, социальная политика, правовые гарантии, молодежь, семьи, здоровье, политика занятости.

To carry out qualified and effective social work, a social worker must have extensive knowledge. This knowledge consists of a system of natural, socio-humanitarian, socio-economic, political and philosophical sciences, and requires knowledge of the characteristics of persons in need of social protection, state policy aimed at supporting them, as well as the activities of state and non-state organizations aimed at protecting personal and legal interests, their cooperation system, and legal guarantees for representatives of each group in need of

social protection. A social worker must be familiar with laws and regulatory documents in his or her activities and know the mechanisms of their implementation.

In particular, today, the establishment of Social Work Departments in higher educational institutions in order to improve the social life of society is being manifested as a form of state social policy aimed directly at improving the social lifestyle of people. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev's Decree No. PF-82 dated June 1, 2023 "On comprehensive measures to provide high-quality social services and assistance to the population and establish an effective control system for them"[1], Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-319 dated September 28, 2023 "On measures to further improve the system of providing social services and assistance to the population"[2], Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 654 dated October 21, 2021 "On measures to further improve the system of social protection of the population" and other regulatory and legal documents indicate the relevance of this area.[3]

The requirements for the knowledge and skills of a social worker are clearly stated in the educational direction "5760100-Social work (in various areas of activity)", approved by order No. 191 of 2008. [4] The State Educational Standard of Higher Education describes the level of preparation and necessary knowledge of bachelors. In accordance with these educational standards, the following knowledge, skills and qualifications are required for a bachelor's degree social work specialist:

General qualification requirements;

Professional qualification requirements.

Bachelors studying in this area must have the following knowledge, skills and qualifications:

- Knowledge of the humanities and socio-economic sciences;
- Knowledge of mathematics and natural sciences;
- Knowledge of general professional sciences;
- Knowledge of specialized sciences, etc.[5]

Knowledge and skills related to the system of disciplines directly related to the profession of social work are presented in the last two blocks. For example, the following requirements are set for some knowledge and skills from the block of requirements for general professional disciplines:

- Social groups and strata, their role in social life. Current problems of various social groups and strata. Methods and directions of conducting social work in separate groups and strata (women, children, the elderly, the disabled, the unemployed, deviant behavior).
- Studying the problems of social groups and strata. Theory of social work and its connection with health. Fundamentals of medical rights and health-related social work.
- Child protection and family policy, the role of women in society. Norms of family and children's rights, elderly policy and features of social assistance to the disabled.
- Employment policy and social work with the unemployed. Educational and psychological principles of social groups and strata, family planning, principles of social protection of the family and problems associated with deviant behavior.[6]

In addition, bachelors of social work should understand the modern achievements of social work, the role of social work among young people, and the importance of social work in

solving youth problems. They should also be ready to develop scientific-methodological, practical recommendations aimed at the constitutional rights of Uzbek youth and the development of social work in society, and work based on world experience.[7]

At the same time, the social work sector operating at the Republican Center for Social Adaptation of Children also develops scientifically-methodologically based recommendations and practical measures aimed at the development of social work.

Conclusion. A broad knowledge base is necessary for the qualified activity of a social worker. Knowledge of social work should cover not only professional skills, but also socio-humanitarian, economic, political and legal spheres. Based on the educational standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan, social work specialists at the bachelor's level must have the necessary knowledge to effectively carry out their activities. Social workers must apply practical and scientific approaches to solving the problems of social groups and strata, as well as be ready to apply modern methodologies and experiences. The development and promotion of social work will help to further improve social protection and support for the youth of Uzbekistan.

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